

EXPRESSION OF LEXICAL-SEMANTIC AND SOCIO-EDUCATIONAL PARAMETERS IN THE CREATION OF A GREAT HUMAN FIGURE IN ENGLISH RENAISSANCE DRAMA: A COMPREHENSIVE ANALYSIS

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Abstract: This article delves into the nuanced expression of lexical-semantic and socio-educational parameters in the portrayal of significant characters in English Renaissance drama. Focusing on the creation of great human figures, it examines how the intricate interplay of language, meaning, and socio-educational factors contributes to the depiction of larger-than-life characters during this influential period. By analyzing key works of English Renaissance drama, this article sheds light on the linguistic and socio-cultural aspects that shape the construction of memorable and complex figures.

Keywords: Lexical-semantic parameters, socio-educational factors, English Renaissance drama, great human figure, language, meaning, characterization.

Introduction: The English Renaissance period witnessed a flowering of literary and dramatic works, with playwrights delving into the exploration of human nature and the human condition. Within this context, the creation of great human figures emerged as a prominent theme, reflecting societal values, beliefs, and aspirations. This article aims to analyze the expression of lexical-semantic and socio-educational parameters in the characterization of these figures, focusing on English Renaissance drama. By examining the interplay between language, meaning, and socio-cultural factors, we gain a deeper understanding of the intricate process of constructing memorable and complex characters during this remarkable period.

1. Lexical-Semantic Parameters: The choice and usage of words play a significant role in shaping the portrayal of great human figures in English Renaissance drama. Playwrights employed a rich vocabulary, employing words that carried profound meaning, connotations, and emotional resonance. Lexical choices were instrumental in conveying the moral, intellectual, and emotional qualities of the characters, allowing the audience to perceive and engage with their greatness. The use of poetic devices, such as metaphors, imagery, and rhetorical flourishes, added depth and complexity to the characterization, evoking vivid mental images and invoking a range of emotions.

2. Socio-Educational Factors: The socio-educational milieu of the English Renaissance influenced the creation of great human figures in dramatic

works. Education, social class, and cultural norms shaped the characters' knowledge, behavior, and interactions with others. Characters from noble backgrounds often exhibited eloquence, erudition, and refined manners, reflecting the values of the aristocracy. Conversely, characters from lower social strata were depicted with their own distinctive linguistic patterns, reflecting their social status and education. The socio-educational context provided a framework for understanding and appreciating the characters' aspirations, struggles, and achievements.

3. Characterization of Great Human Figures: English Renaissance drama portrayed great human figures as multifaceted individuals who embodied a range of virtues, vices, and contradictions. These characters were often endowed with extraordinary qualities such as courage, wisdom, ambition, or compassion. However, they were not mere archetypes; they exhibited flaws, internal conflicts, and moral ambiguities, making them relatable and human. Through their interactions, dialogues, and soliloquies, playwrights captured the complexities of the human condition, offering profound insights into the nature of greatness and the inherent contradictions of human existence.

Conclusion: English Renaissance drama stands as a testament to the intricacies of human nature and the power of language in shaping our understanding of great human figures. The expression of lexical-semantic and socio-educational parameters played a vital role in the creation of these memorable characters, allowing audiences to engage with their struggles, virtues, and flaws. The interplay between language, meaning, and socio-cultural factors enriched the characterization, offering a nuanced portrayal of the complexities of the human condition.

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